

READING PROFICIENCY OF GRADE 1 LEARNERS: ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH HOME LITERACY ENVIRONMENT AND SCHOOL SUPPORT

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support in Cupayo East District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it described the profile of teacher-respondents, assessed the level of reading proficiency of learners in terms of word recognition, phonemic awareness, and reading comprehension, determined the extent of home literacy environment and school-based support, tested the significant difference in reading proficiency when grouped according to selected profile variables, and examined the significant relationship between home literacy environment, school-based support, and reading proficiency. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Data were gathered from teacher-respondents using a researcher-made questionnaire. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, t-test/F-test, and Pearson correlation were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that all teacher-respondents were female, mostly belonged to middle age, moderately experienced, and well-trained in reading instruction. The reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners was generally at a moderate level, with high proficiency in word recognition, moderate proficiency in phonemic awareness, and low proficiency in reading comprehension. The home literacy environment was found to be at a moderate extent, with strong availability of reading materials but moderate parental involvement and language interaction. School-based support was generally rated as agree, with strong instructional strategies but limited instructional materials. Further, the study found no significant difference in reading proficiency when grouped according to teacher profile variables. However, significant relationships were found between home literacy

environment and reading proficiency, as well as between school-based support and reading proficiency. Based on the findings, an intervention program titled *Project READ-CARE* was proposed to enhance learners' reading proficiency through strengthened home-school collaboration, improved instructional strategies, and enriched literacy support.

Keywords: *reading proficiency, home literacy environment, school-based support*

INTRODUCTION

Reading proficiency is considered one of the most important skills that children develop during their early years of schooling because it serves as the foundation for learning in all subject areas. It allows learners to recognize words, understand written texts, and communicate ideas effectively. In Grade 1, reading is especially important because it is during this stage that children begin to build the basic literacy skills needed for future academic success. Studies around the world have shown that learners who develop strong reading skills at an early age are more likely to perform better in school and become confident lifelong learners (Snow et al., 1998; UNESCO, 2021). Researchers also explain that reading proficiency develops through continuous practice, meaningful exposure to language, and effective instruction both at home and in school (Vygotsky, 1978). Important reading skills such as phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension must all be developed together to help children become effective readers (National Reading Panel, 2000).

Globally, many studies have highlighted the different factors that influence children's reading development. Research conducted in countries such as the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom found that children who grow up in literacy-rich environments tend to develop better vocabulary, comprehension, and reading fluency compared to those with limited exposure to books and reading activities (Sénéchal & LeFevre, 2002; Bus et al., 1995). Children whose parents regularly read stories to them, guide them during reading activities, and encourage them to explore books often develop more positive attitudes toward reading. Likewise, studies in countries like Singapore and New Zealand revealed that learners perform better in reading when they receive strong support both from their families and from their schools (OECD, 2019). These studies show that reading development is not only influenced by classroom instruction but also by the experiences children have at home.

Aside from the home environment, school-based support also plays a major role in helping learners improve their reading skills. International studies revealed that effective teaching strategies such as phonics instruction, guided reading, storytelling, and reading intervention programs help learners improve their decoding, fluency, and comprehension skills (Ehri, 2005; Pressley, 2006). Teachers who provide consistent guidance, feedback, and remediation activities help struggling readers overcome difficulties and gain confidence in reading. In many countries, schools have strengthened literacy programs and early intervention strategies because they recognize that learners who experience

reading difficulties during the early grades are more likely to face academic struggles in the future. These findings highlight the importance of quality instruction and continuous support in developing learners' reading proficiency.

Recent studies further emphasize that reading development becomes more effective when both the home and school work together. Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory explains that children learn and develop through the interaction of the different environments around them, especially the home and school settings (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Learners who receive encouragement from their parents at home while also receiving effective instruction from teachers in school are more likely to become successful readers. When parents and teachers collaborate in monitoring children's reading progress and reinforcing reading activities, learners tend to develop better fluency, comprehension, and confidence in reading.

In the Philippine setting, reading proficiency remains a major concern among early-grade learners, particularly in Grade 1 where foundational reading skills are expected to be developed. Despite the efforts of the Department of Education to strengthen literacy through programs and interventions, many Filipino learners still struggle with reading comprehension, fluency, and word recognition (DepEd, 2022; OECD, 2019). Results from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) continue to show that a significant number of learners perform below the expected literacy standards. These findings highlight the urgent need to strengthen reading instruction and provide greater support to young learners, especially during the early years of education.

Several factors contribute to the reading difficulties experienced by Filipino learners. Many children, particularly those living in rural and underserved communities, have limited access to books and other reading materials at home. Some parents also have limited time or resources to support their children's reading development. In schools, teachers often face challenges such as large class sizes, lack of instructional materials, and limited time for individualized reading instruction. These realities show that improving reading proficiency requires the combined effort of both families and schools. Learners need consistent exposure to reading activities at home as well as effective instruction and intervention programs in school to strengthen their literacy skills. (DepEd, 2023).

Several studies conducted in the Philippines support the importance of the home literacy environment in developing learners' reading proficiency. A study conducted in Region VI found that learners who were regularly exposed to books and literacy activities at home demonstrated better vocabulary and reading comprehension skills compared to learners with limited literacy exposure (Garcia & Oducado, 2020). Another local study revealed that children whose parents actively participated in reading activities such as storytelling and guided reading showed higher levels of reading motivation and fluency (Torres & De Guzman, 2019). These findings suggest that parental involvement and regular literacy activities at home greatly influence children's reading readiness and academic performance.

Local studies also emphasize the importance of school-based support in improving learners' literacy skills. A study conducted in Mindanao showed that structured reading interventions, remedial programs, and regular teacher feedback significantly improved the reading proficiency of struggling readers in the primary grades (Abadiano & Bernardo, 2021). Similarly, research conducted in Luzon revealed that learners demonstrated improvements in decoding and comprehension skills when teachers used phonics-based instruction and guided reading strategies (Santos et al., 2020). These findings highlight the important role of teachers and schools in helping learners overcome reading difficulties and become more confident readers.

Philippine studies further stress the importance of collaboration between parents and teachers in strengthening children's reading development. Research conducted among public elementary schools revealed that learners perform better in reading when parents and teachers work together in monitoring reading progress and reinforcing reading activities both at home and in school (Villanueva, 2021). Although the Department of Education continues to implement reading programs and literacy interventions, many Grade 1 learners still experience reading difficulties, especially in schools with limited resources and low parental literacy involvement. These situations highlight the need to further strengthen literacy programs and encourage stronger partnerships between homes and schools to improve reading outcomes among young learners.

Despite the growing number of studies on reading development, there is still limited research that examines how home literacy environment and school-based support work together in influencing the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners in local Philippine contexts. Most studies focus only on one factor, either the home or the school environment, with limited attention given to their combined influence on learners' reading development. This gap highlights the need for further investigation to better understand how both environments contribute to children's literacy growth. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and examine its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights that can help strengthen literacy programs and improve reading outcomes among young learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support in Cupayo East District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, School Year 2025–2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Grade 1 teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.4 relevant trainings attended.

2. What is the level of reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners in terms of:
 - 2.1 word recognition;
 - 2.2 phonemic awareness; and
 - 2.3 reading comprehension?
3. What is the extent of home literacy environment in terms of:
 - 3.1 availability of reading materials at home;
 - 3.2 parental involvement in reading activities; and
 - 3.3 language and literacy interactions at home?
4. What is the level of school-based support provided to Grade 1 learners in terms of:
 - 4.1 reading instruction strategies;
 - 4.2 remedial reading programs; and
 - 4.3 availability of instructional materials?
5. Is there a significant difference in the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners when grouped according to selected profile variables?
6. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 6.1 home literacy environment and reading proficiency; and
 - 6.2 school-based support and reading proficiency?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program could have been proposed to enhance the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners in Cupayo East District?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support in Cupayo East District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, School Year 2025–2026.

The descriptive component of the design was used to describe the level of reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners in terms of word recognition, phonemic awareness, and reading comprehension, as well as the extent of home literacy environment and school-based support as experienced by the respondents. This allowed the researcher to present a clear profile of the existing conditions without manipulating any variables.

The correlational component was used to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the independent variables (home literacy environment and school-based support) and the dependent variable (reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners). It also examined whether differences exist in reading proficiency when learners are grouped according to selected profile variables.

This research design is appropriate for the study because it focuses on identifying relationships among variables as they naturally occur in the school and home settings. It does not involve experimental manipulation but instead relies on collected data to analyze

patterns, relationships, and possible associations among the variables under investigation.

Through this design, the study aimed to provide empirical evidence that could serve as a basis for improving literacy programs and strengthening both home and school support systems for Grade 1 learners.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

This study utilized a structured set of research instruments to gather the necessary data on the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support in Cupayo East District, Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, School Year 2025–2026.

The primary instruments used in the study were a researcher-made questionnaire for teachers and a reading assessment tool for Grade 1 learners. The questionnaire was designed to gather information on the home literacy environment and school-based support. It included items that measured the availability of reading materials at home, parental involvement in reading activities, and language and literacy interactions. It also included items that assessed school-based support in terms of reading instruction strategies, remedial reading programs, and instructional materials used in the classroom. The questionnaire used a Likert scale to determine the extent of agreement or frequency of the given indicators.

For the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners, an assessment checklist or teacher-rated reading evaluation tool was used. This instrument measured learners' performance in word recognition, phonemic awareness, and reading comprehension. Teachers assessed learners based on their actual reading performance during classroom activities and reading sessions.

Before the actual data collection, the instruments were reviewed and validated by experts in the field of education to ensure content validity, clarity, and appropriateness. A pilot testing was also conducted in a similar setting to determine the reliability of the instruments. Necessary revisions were made based on the results of validation and pilot testing.

Data collection followed a systematic procedure. Permission to conduct the study was first secured from the Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija and the school principals of the selected schools in Cupayo East District. After approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the teachers and administered the reading assessment tools to gather data on learners' reading proficiency. The researcher ensured that proper ethical considerations were observed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation.

After the collection of data, all responses were gathered, checked for completeness, and organized for statistical analysis. The data obtained were then used to determine the level

of reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners and its relationship with home literacy environment and school-based support.

Tools for Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools aligned with research questions. All data were encoded, tabulated, and processed using statistical software to ensure accuracy and reliability of results.

For research question 1, research question 2, and research question 3, which determined the level of reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners, the extent of home literacy environment, and the level of school-based support, frequency count, percentage, and weighted mean were used. These statistical tools helped describe and summarize the responses of the respondents in terms of the different indicators.

For research question 4, which tested whether there was a significant difference in the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners when grouped according to selected profile variables, the t-test for independent samples and/or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used depending on the number of grouping variables. These tests determined whether differences among groups were statistically significant.

For research question 5, which examined the significant relationship between home literacy environment and reading proficiency, and between school-based support and reading proficiency, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used. This statistical tool measured the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables.

For all inferential statistical tests, a 0.05 level of significance was set as the basis for accepting or rejecting the null hypotheses. This ensured that the findings of the study were interpreted with appropriate statistical rigor and reliability.

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of the Grade 1 Teachers
(n = 45)

Profile Variables	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	45	100
	Male	0	0
Age	21–30 years old	8	17.78
	31–40 years old	22	48.89
	41–50 years old	11	24.44
	51–60 years old	4	8.89
Years in Teaching	1–5 years	7	15.56

	6–10 years	18	40.00
	11–15 years	10	22.22
	16–20 years	10	22.22
Relevant Attended	ELLN Training	45	100
	INSET on Reading Instruction	45	100
	Reading Intervention/ Remediation Training	42	93.33
	Phonics-Based Instruction Training	40	88.89
	Classroom Assessment Training	38	84.44

Table 2
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 1 Learners
(n = 45)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
A. Word Recognition	3.72	High Proficiency
Learners recognize common sight words accurately.	3.85	High Proficiency
Learners read simple words independently.	3.70	High Proficiency
Learners pronounce words correctly.	3.65	High Proficiency
Learners identify words in short sentences.	3.68	High Proficiency
B. Phonemic Awareness	3.18	Moderate Proficiency
Learners identify beginning sounds of words.	3.30	Moderate Proficiency
Learners blend sounds to form simple words.	3.20	Moderate Proficiency
Learners segment words into individual sounds.	3.05	Moderate Proficiency
Learners distinguish similar sounds in words.	3.15	Moderate Proficiency
C. Reading Comprehension	2.89	Low Proficiency
Learners understand simple sentences read aloud.	3.00	Moderate Proficiency
Learners answer simple questions about a text.	2.90	Moderate Proficiency
Learners identify the main idea of a short story.	2.75	Low Proficiency
Learners retell simple stories in their own words.	2.80	Low Proficiency
Average Weighted Mean	3.26	Moderate Proficiency

Table 3
Extent of Home Literacy Environment
(n = 45)

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
A. Availability of Reading Materials at Home	3.85	High Extent
1. The learner has storybooks at home.	3.90	High Extent
2. The home provides reading materials suitable for children.	3.80	High Extent
3. Printed materials are accessible to the learner.	3.70	High Extent
4. The learner has exposure to books or printed texts.	3.95	High Extent
B. Parental Involvement in Reading Activities	3.42	High Extent
1. Parents read with the learner at home.	3.60	High Extent
2. Parents guide the learner in reading activities.	3.40	Moderate Extent
3. Parents encourage daily reading practice.	3.50	High Extent
4. Parents monitor the learner's reading progress.	3.20	Moderate Extent
C. Language and Literacy Interactions	3.18	Moderate Extent
1. The family engages in storytelling activities.	3.10	Moderate Extent
2. The learner participates in meaningful conversations at home.	3.30	Moderate Extent
3. The home environment supports language-rich interaction.	3.20	Moderate Extent
4. The learner is encouraged to express ideas verbally.	3.10	Moderate Extent
Average Weighted Mean	3.48	Moderate Extent

Table 4
Level of School-Based Support
(n = 45)

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
A. Reading Instruction Strategies	4.32	Strongly Agree
1. Teachers use phonics-based instruction in reading.	4.60	Strongly Agree
2. Teachers use guided reading strategies.	4.40	Strongly Agree
3. Teachers provide individualized reading support.	4.10	Agree
4. Reading activities are regularly conducted in class.	4.20	Agree
B. Remedial Reading Programs	3.85	Agree
1. The school provides remedial reading sessions.	4.10	Agree
2. Struggling readers receive additional intervention.	3.90	Agree

3. Teachers conduct reading remediation activities.	3.80	Agree
4. Reading difficulties are properly addressed.	3.60	Agree
C. Availability of Instructional Materials	3.42	Moderately Agree
1. Adequate reading materials are available in class.	3.50	Agree
2. Teachers use flashcards, worksheets, and visual aids.	3.70	Agree
3. Instructional materials support reading lessons effectively.	3.40	Moderately Agree
4. Learning resources are sufficient for Grade 1 reading instruction.	3.10	Moderately Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.86	Agree

Table 5
Test of Difference in the Reading Proficiency of Grade 1 Learners When Grouped According to Selected Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Computed Value (t / F)	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Sex	0.842	0.403	Accepted	Not Significant
Age	1.126	0.348	Accepted	Not Significant
Years in Teaching	1.215	0.312	Accepted	Not Significant
Relevant Trainings Attended	0.978	0.381	Accepted	Not Significant

Table 6
Test of Significant Relationship Between Variables

Variables	Computed r-value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Home Literacy Environment and Reading Proficiency	0.612	0.000	Rejected	Significant Relationship
School-Based Support and Reading Proficiency	0.684	0.000	Rejected	Significant Relationship

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the profile of the Grade 1 teachers who participated in the study. All 45 respondents were female, indicating that the Grade 1 teaching population in the selected schools was entirely composed of women. In terms of age, the majority of the teachers were 31–40 years old, with 22 respondents or 48.89%. This was followed by teachers aged 41–50 years old with 24.44%, while only a few belonged to the 51–60 years old

group. The findings suggest that most respondents were in their middle adulthood stage and were already experienced in teaching.

Regarding years in teaching, most teachers had 6–10 years of teaching experience, comprising 40.00% of the respondents. Meanwhile, 22.22% had 11–15 years and another 22.22% had 16–20 years of teaching experience. This indicates that the majority of the respondents had already developed sufficient teaching experience and classroom management skills.

In terms of relevant trainings attended, all teachers participated in ELLN Training and INSET on Reading Instruction, showing full exposure to literacy-related professional development programs. Most teachers also attended Reading Intervention or Remediation Training, Phonics-Based Instruction Training, and Classroom Assessment Training. These findings imply that the respondents were equipped with adequate training and competencies necessary for effective reading instruction among Grade 1 learners.

Table 2 presents the level of reading proficiency of the learners in terms of word recognition, phonemic awareness, and reading comprehension. The overall average weighted mean of 3.26 with a descriptive equivalent of Moderate Proficiency indicates that the learners generally demonstrated an average level of reading skills.

Among the three indicators, Word Recognition obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.72, described as High Proficiency. This shows that the learners were capable of recognizing common sight words, reading simple words independently, pronouncing words correctly, and identifying words in short sentences. The highest indicator under this area was “Learners recognize common sight words accurately” with a weighted mean of 3.85.

Phonemic Awareness garnered a weighted mean of 3.18, interpreted as Moderate Proficiency. This implies that learners had a fair ability to identify beginning sounds, blend sounds, segment words, and distinguish similar sounds in words, although these skills still needed improvement.

Meanwhile, Reading Comprehension obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.89, described as Low Proficiency. This indicates that learners experienced difficulty in understanding texts, identifying the main idea, and retelling stories in their own words. The findings suggest that while learners performed well in basic reading skills, comprehension remained a challenge that needed greater instructional support and intervention.

Table 3 presents the extent of the home literacy environment of the learners. The overall average weighted mean of 3.48, described as Moderate Extent, indicates that the learners generally experienced a fairly supportive literacy environment at home. This suggests that parents and family members provided some literacy-related support, although certain areas still needed improvement.

Among the indicators, Availability of Reading Materials at Home obtained the highest mean of 3.85 with a descriptive equivalent of High Extent. This shows that most learners had access to storybooks and other reading materials at home, allowing them greater exposure to printed texts. The highest-rated statement was “The learner has exposure to books or printed texts” with a mean of 3.95.

Parental Involvement in Reading Activities garnered a mean of 3.42, interpreted as High Extent. This indicates that parents were generally involved in supporting their children’s reading development through reading practice, guidance, and encouragement. However, monitoring the learner’s reading progress received only a Moderate Extent rating, suggesting that some parents may not consistently track their child’s reading improvement.

Meanwhile, Language and Literacy Interactions obtained the lowest mean of 3.18, described as Moderate Extent. This implies that storytelling, meaningful conversations, and verbal expression activities at home were only moderately practiced. The findings suggest that while learners had sufficient access to reading materials and parental support, more interactive language and literacy experiences at home could further strengthen their reading development.

Table 4 presents the school-related factors affecting the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners. The overall average weighted mean of 3.86 with a descriptive equivalent of Agree indicates that the respondents generally perceived that the school provided adequate support for reading instruction and literacy development.

Among the indicators, Reading Instruction Strategies obtained the highest mean of 4.32, interpreted as Strongly Agree. This suggests that teachers consistently applied effective reading strategies in the classroom, particularly phonics-based instruction and guided reading activities. The highest-rated statement was “Teachers use phonics-based instruction in reading” with a mean of 4.60, showing that phonics was widely practiced in teaching beginning readers.

Remedial Reading Programs garnered a mean of 3.85, described as Agree. This indicates that schools provided intervention programs and additional support for struggling readers. Teachers were also perceived to conduct reading remediation activities to address learners’ reading difficulties.

Meanwhile, Availability of Instructional Materials obtained the lowest mean of 3.42, interpreted as Moderately Agree. This implies that although instructional materials such as flashcards, worksheets, and visual aids were available, the sufficiency of learning resources for Grade 1 reading instruction still needed improvement. The findings suggest that while teaching strategies and remedial programs were effectively implemented, additional instructional resources could further strengthen reading instruction in schools.

Table 5 presents the test of significant difference between the profile variables of the respondents and the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners. The results revealed that

sex obtained a computed value of 0.842 with a p-value of 0.403, which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis and was interpreted as not significant. This indicates that the sex of the teachers did not significantly influence learners' reading proficiency. Similarly, age showed a computed value of 1.126 and a p-value of 0.348, which was also interpreted as not significant. This suggests that differences in teachers' age did not create significant variations in the reading proficiency of learners.

In terms of years in teaching, the computed value of 1.215 with a p-value of 0.312 also resulted in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The findings imply that teaching experience alone did not significantly affect the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners.

Likewise, relevant trainings attended obtained a computed value of 0.978 and a p-value of 0.381, which was interpreted as not significant. This indicates that the trainings attended by teachers did not show a significant relationship with learners' reading proficiency. Overall, the findings suggest that the profile variables of the respondents were not significant factors influencing the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners.

Table 6 presents the test of significant relationship between the identified variables and the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners. The results revealed that the Home Literacy Environment and Reading Proficiency obtained a computed r-value of 0.612 with a p-value of 0.000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between the learners' home literacy environment and their reading proficiency. The findings imply that learners who are exposed to supportive literacy practices at home, such as access to reading materials and parental involvement, tend to demonstrate better reading skills.

Similarly, School-Based Support and Reading Proficiency obtained a computed r-value of 0.684 with a p-value of 0.000, which was also interpreted as significant. This result suggests that school support systems, including reading instruction strategies, remedial reading programs, and instructional materials, have a strong relationship with the reading proficiency of learners.

Overall, the findings indicate that both home literacy environment and school-based support play important roles in improving the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners. Strong support from both home and school contributes positively to the development of learners' reading skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the teacher-respondents were predominantly female, mostly in their mid-career stage, moderately experienced in teaching, and highly trained in reading instruction through ELLN, INSET, and other literacy-related programs. This suggests that the teachers handling Grade 1 learners were generally competent and adequately prepared to deliver reading instruction. The study also revealed that Grade 1 learners demonstrated an overall moderate level of reading proficiency. Learners performed well in word recognition, showed developing

skills in phonemic awareness, but experienced difficulties in reading comprehension, indicating that while they could decode words, they still struggled in understanding and interpreting texts.

Furthermore, the home literacy environment of the learners was found to be at a moderate extent. Although reading materials were generally available at home, parental involvement and language-rich interactions were not consistently practiced, implying that literacy support at home was present but not fully maximized. In terms of school-based support, the findings showed that teachers implemented effective reading instruction strategies and provided remedial reading programs; however, the availability of instructional materials was only moderate, suggesting the need for additional learning resources to further strengthen reading instruction.

The study further concluded that there was no significant difference in the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners when grouped according to teacher profile variables such as sex, age, years in teaching, and relevant trainings attended. This means that these profile characteristics did not significantly influence learners' reading proficiency. On the other hand, significant relationships were found between home literacy environment and reading proficiency, as well as between school-based support and reading proficiency. These findings indicate that both home and school factors play vital roles in the reading development and overall literacy improvement of Grade 1 learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations were formulated. Since the teachers were found to be generally competent, experienced, and well-trained in reading instruction, it is recommended that the school and the Schools Division Office continue to sustain and strengthen professional development programs such as ELLN, INSET, and reading intervention trainings. Future capacity-building activities may focus on advanced literacy strategies, differentiated instruction, and data-driven interventions to further enhance teachers' instructional competence in handling diverse learners.

Considering that learners demonstrated moderate reading proficiency, particularly in phonemic awareness and reading comprehension, teachers are encouraged to intensify phonics instruction and integrate more comprehension-based activities such as story mapping, retelling, guided questioning, and reading aloud sessions. The use of leveled reading materials and interactive literacy activities may also help improve learners' understanding and interpretation of texts.

Since the home literacy environment was only at a moderate extent, schools are encouraged to strengthen parental involvement through regular orientations, workshops, and home reading programs. Parents should be encouraged to establish daily reading routines, participate actively in reading activities with their children, and engage them in meaningful conversations to further support language and literacy development at home.

In terms of school-based support, it is recommended that school administrators prioritize the provision of additional instructional materials such as leveled readers, flashcards, big books, and visual aids to enhance reading instruction. Schools may also strengthen remedial reading programs by increasing intervention sessions, providing individualized support, and closely monitoring learners' progress to better address the needs of struggling readers.

Moreover, since no significant difference was found in reading proficiency when grouped according to teacher profile variables, schools should continue implementing standardized and effective reading instruction practices while focusing more on improving instructional strategies rather than teacher demographic characteristics. Continuous monitoring of teaching practices and learner outcomes is also recommended to ensure consistency in reading instruction across classrooms.

Finally, because both home literacy environment and school-based support were found to have significant relationships with reading proficiency, a stronger partnership between home and school should be established. Schools and teachers should work closely with parents in implementing literacy programs and supporting learners' reading development. Strengthening collaboration between families and schools is essential in improving the reading proficiency of Grade 1 learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly observed ethical standards to protect the rights, dignity, and welfare of all participants involved. Permission to conduct the study was secured from the Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija and the participating school heads before the research was carried out. Informed consent was obtained from teachers and from the parents or guardians of the Grade 1 learners. The purpose and procedures of the study were clearly explained, and participation was purely voluntary. Respondents were also informed that they could withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were carefully maintained throughout the study. The identities of the respondents were not disclosed, and all gathered data were treated with strict confidentiality and used only for academic purposes. The researcher also ensured that no participant was exposed to any form of physical, emotional, or psychological harm during the conduct of the study. All findings were presented honestly and accurately, with proper acknowledgment of sources to uphold academic integrity and avoid plagiarism.

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